

Influence of Online Assessment Methods on Students' Outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt Study Centre.

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Abstract

This study investigated influence of online assessment methods on students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre. Three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population and sample of the study was 73 facilitators consisting of 41 males and 32 females from Port Harcourt study centre. The instrument was a fifteen (15) items self-developed questionnaire titled: "Influence of Online Assessment Methods on Students' Outcome Questionnaire" which was face and content validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation and Department of Educational Management. Cronbach Alpha was used to establish the reliability of the instrument which yielded reliability indexes of 0.72, 0.86 and 0.84. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-test was used in testing the formulated null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that to a high extent online quizzes, online discussion and peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that facilitators should design online quizzes that align closely with course objectives and incorporate a variety of question types to cater for diverse learning styles.

Key Words: Online Assessment Methods, Students' Learning Outcomes, Open and Distance Learning, Assessment, Online Quizzes, Online Discussion, Peer Assessment

INTRODUCTION

Tertiary education holds significant importance in Nigeria, serving as the educational level children receive after secondary education. According to Amie-Ogan and Epelle (2023), tertiary education is the level of education that equips students with requisite knowledge, skills and abilities as well as rekindles such entrepreneurial spirit to aid them emerge as a force to reckon with in the world of work and self-reliance. This suggests that the expertise, skills, knowledge and ideas gained through years of tertiary education gives Nigerian graduates competitive advantage over their peers globally. Paul and Amadi (2017), asserted that tertiary education is saddled with the responsibility of producing intellectuals, researchers and required general workforce needed for societal development. The Federal Republic of Nigeria in her National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) stated succinctly that tertiary education is education given after Post Basic Education in institutions such as the Universities and Inter University Centres such as the Nigerian French Language Village, Nigerian Arabic Language Village, National Institute of Nigerian Languages, Colleges of Education, Monotechnics, Polytechnics and other specialized institutions such as Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs), Agriculture, Schools of Health and Technology and the National Teachers Institutes (NTI).

The provision of quality education to millions has been one of the major struggles facing developing countries like Nigeria. The increasing growth in Nigeria's population and high demand for tertiary education have meant that the country must of necessity find the effective means to address the significant unmet demand for education. The Executive Secretary, National Universities Commission (NUC), Prof. Abubakar Rasheed, while presenting provisional licenses to some newly established private universities in Abuja revealed that Nigeria now has 264 universities (Punch Newspaper, 2023). The number includes universities owned by federal and state governments as well as private individuals and corporations. These universities have practically not met the ever-increasing demand for university education through the formal classroom-bound learning mode (Osuji, Epelle & Alabere, 2023). Jegede (2016) stated that data available indicates that institutions of higher learning have only been able to cope, on the average, with about 20 per cent of admission demands implying that over 80 per cent of candidates who apply to universities cannot be accommodated, not necessarily because they are not qualified but due to

gross inadequacies in resources and facilities. This development implies that in the very near future, the inadequate facilities would be further stretched arising from the demand for university education. This strongly support the rationale behind the establishment of open and distance learning institutions like the National Open University in 1983 as a means of improving educational standards and succour for those who missed access to the conventional schooling.

Open and distance learning is a non-barrier education mode with the aim to bridge the time, space, economic, social, educational and communication distance between students and the institution. Liguori and Winkler (2020) defined open and distance learning as the type of educational system in which the teacher and student communicate through various media to exchange information, such as publications and educational media, using modern audio-visual technologies. According to Osuji and Bakpo (2022) open and distance learning is a learning situation where the learners are geographically separated from the facilitators. The widespread adoption of this mode of learning have significantly transformed the landscape of education in Nigeria. This transition has prompted educators to explore the impact of online assessment methods within this unique educational framework. The traditional brick-and-mortar model of education often relies heavily on in-person assessments, such as written exams and practical demonstrations (Tait, 2018). However, the digital landscape of open and distance learning offers a myriad of alternative assessment methods, including online quizzes, discussions, peer evaluations and multimedia projects. Conole (2019) stated that understanding how these diverse assessment approaches influence students' outcomes is essential for educators. It requires examining factors such as student engagement, knowledge retention, academic performance and overall satisfaction with the learning experience. Therefore, it is to be expected that a change in assessment format from a face-to-face method to an online method will have some impact on students' outcome.

The term “students outcome” refers to the desired learning objectives or standard that students are expected to achieve. Osuji and Bakpo (2022) defined students outcome as the intended goals of a course programme or learning experience that students are expected to achieve by the school or institution. In classrooms be it conventional or mediated, students perform their potentials effectively as a result of it, learning takes place. The learning outcomes changes the behaviour pattern of the students through different subject. When students meet the expectation of a learning programme, then such students are said to have positive learning outcome, while the reverse is the case when students' expectations are not met. However, in this study the characteristics of a good open and distance learning relies on the instructors' ability to providing appropriate learning resources, possessing effective communication ability, providing necessary theoretical and practical knowledge, and encouraging critical thinking among learners. Also, students' outcome have been articulated to include the ability of students to understand content taught in a clear and understandable manner, been able to have appropriate, relevant and timely communication with the instructor, ability to acquire theoretical and practical knowledge, and the ability to think critically. These concern however is rested on the assessment methods adopted in the open and distance learning institutions like the National Open University in Nigeria.

Assessment is a process of observation and examination through which quality is intended to be tested. According to Berker (2017), it comprises of all activities to help learners recall what has been impacted to them, for example, tests, assignments, demonstration, illustration, and others on large scale or classroom level. Assessment in open and distance learning is carried out online since this mode of learning provides a flexible learning opportunities for learners using varieties of media including electronic print, online printing, study guides, course guides, videos, recordings, software and online information. Heil and Ifenthaler (2023) define online assessment as an electronic method of gathering information about a learner and learning processes to draw inferences about the learner's dispositions.

Online assessment has several benefits such as the capacity to offer students immediate feedback to help them improve their knowledge and performance, the capacity to access it from various geographical locations at times depending on the student's convenience, and the capacity to take assessment tests multiple times to evaluate and refine their knowledge (Sikurajapathi, Henderson & Gwynllyw, 2020). Bahar and Asil (2018) opined that online assessment refers to the use of digital technology for the evaluation, design, feedback and storage of results. The awareness that assessment can improve education and help determine the learning outcomes of the individuals is an important instrument to assure that students attain the learning goals effectively. Hiruni, Dinushika, Chalani, Kerthiga, Munasinghe and Nilmini (2023) noted that online assessment offers variety of assessment methods which include online quizzes, online discussions and peer assessment. These online assessment methods cater to

the unique needs of distance learners, providing flexibility, interactivity and opportunities for self-directed learning while effectively evaluating students' knowledge and skills.

Online quizzes is a multi-choice or short-answer assessment method administered for immediate feedback. Online quizzes is a type of electronic assessment method in which students are asked to select the correct answer from the choices listed (Güler, 2017). Online quizzes is one of the assessment methods in an online learning environment that gives feedback on whether a learner is progressing in line with the course objectives or assistance is required to achieve success (Roediger, Putnam & Smith, 2019). This assessment method have many benefits that can be used effectively at any stage of the learning process. It helps learners succeed individually by sharpening their focus and fostering deeper thinking.

Bognár, Fauszt and Váraljai (2021) asserted that online quizzes strongly influence students' attitude on learning as a result, students perceive themselves as being more prepared for class meeting and more prepared for class assessments. Online quizzes provide immediate feedback to students, while the feedback from paper-and-pencil quizzes takes longer to reach them. Students seem to appreciate online quizzes due to its immediate feedback because, through them, they are able to verify their own knowledge of a particular subject (Bälter, Enström, & Klingenberg, 2018). After taking online quizzes, students are able to immediately compare their actual knowledge with the knowledge they thought they had. Nicol (2017) stated that online quizzes increase students' motivation and provides the opportunity for them to revise specific topics to catch up. As a result, students are encouraged to study continuously over a term.

Online discussions is another digital assessment method that is used in virtual and blended learning environments. Cambridge Assessment International Education (2020) referred to online discussion as an active assessment approach i.e., "an approach where learners participate in the learning process by building knowledge and understanding". Learners play an active role and take responsibility for their own learning during online discussions. This approach may motivate learners to participate in class more by adding to discussions and asking questions (Connor-Greene, 2020). Biriya and Thomas in Lyu (2018) argue that increased student participation is one of the immediate benefits of participating in online discussions as it influences interaction and communication between students themselves and between students and the teacher significantly.

The flexible nature of online discussions enhances the quality of students' responses positively. It constitutes a valuable opportunity for shy and reserved students to contribute their opinions about a variety of topics, which boosts their confidence and promotes their learning (Onyema, Deborah, AlSayed, Naveed, & Sanober, 2019). When compared to a traditional classroom discussion which requires instant replies from students, online discussions afford students ample time to reflect on their answers before posting them for others to read. In online discussion platform, learners often negotiate friendship with other like-minded learners. They often read and comment on their discussion postings and seek to build friendship with them outside the teaching-learning context. Furthermore, online discussion make learners take ownership of their own learning as they make decisions about the postings to read, the questions to ask, and the comments to post, among other tasks a discussion requires (Harris & Sander, 2017).

Another online assessment method in a blended learning environment is the peer assessment. Peer assessment is a process in which students' work are being evaluated by another student of similar status. Obilor and Adegbeye (2021) asserted that peer assessment is the process whereby students grade assignments or tests of their mates or peers based on a teacher's benchmarks. They further stated that it provides a structured learning process for students to critique and provide feedback to each other on their work. This process enable learners reflect on their own efforts as well as enrich this reflection by exchanging feedback on their own and their peers' works. According to Kreber, Anderson, Enthwhistle and McArthur (2014) peer assessment support and enhance learning outcome in both the students who receive the feedback and in those who give it, because the activity triggers critical reasoning with a focus on the artefacts produced by both. Peer assessment provides qualitative feedback that guide and help students in the revision of their work. It helps students develop lifelong skills in assessing and providing feedback to others. It also equips them with skills to self-assess and improve their life (Smither in Ugorji & King-Agboto, 2023). The capacity to produce quality feedback is a fundamental skill that should be developed in students because it is an essential component of their learning outcomes.

Peer assessment helps the students to understand the deeper sense of the criteria to help direct their learning towards successful achievements. Orsmond (2015) asserted that engaging students in peer assessment can help

them in learning to evaluate their own learning and in interpreting assessment criteria. Amendola and Miceli (2018) found evidence that students participating in peer assessment developed their skills of making reasoned justification of arguments. In the same vein, Macpherson in Fellenz (2016) found indications of a growth in the students' reflective and critical thinking skills after participating in a peer assessment in which the students were to give feedback on each other's literature reviews. Further benefits might also include increasing feedback to students; giving students a sense of ownership of assessment process and encouraging critical analysis of students' work. Adeyemi (2012) reported that the use of peer assessment enhance students' self-efficacy and promotes learner's autonomy.

Statement of the Problem

The National Open University, characterized by its openness, flexibility and use of technology offers unique opportunities in delivering quality education to diverse student population who often juggle studies with work and family responsibilities. It is a basic requirement in open and distance learning programme for students to undergo assessment to collect data on the learner and their learning processes, enabling insights into the learner's tendencies. Online assessment methods play crucial role in this context, providing means to evaluate students learning remotely while accommodating the flexibility and accessibility demanded by distance learners. As distance education continues to expand globally, there is a growing interest in understanding how different online assessment methods impact students' outcome.

Currently, there is a general perception that online assessment in National Open University present its own set of challenges, such as increased preparation efforts, technical glitches, lack of face-to-face interaction and the issue of cheating (Alsadoon in Dada, Zaifada & Ofie, 2020). However, exploratory studies shows that facilitators in National Open University face a multitude of challenges such as additional time for creating question banks, limited supervision to ensure that students do not engage in cheating, creating assessment that accurately measure students' understanding and skills and addressing technical glitches when assessing students, as they are not in a position where they have direct contact with the students as perceived in conventional classroom. These inadequacies are having adverse effects on the assessment process. Addressing these challenges requires instructors to employ a variety of assessment strategies. Based on this, the researcher investigated influence of online assessment methods on students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate influence of online assessment methods on students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the extent to which online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.
2. ascertain the extent to which online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.
3. examine the extent to which peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre?
2. To what extent does online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre?
3. To what extent does peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre?

Hypothesis

- Ho₁ There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

- Ho₂ There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.
- Ho₃ There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 73 facilitators consisting of 41 males and 32 females from Port Harcourt study centre. The entire population was used due to its manageable size which infers census. The instrument for the study was a structured questionnaire titled: "Influence of Online Assessment Methods on Students' Outcome Questionnaire (IOAMSOQ)" which was face and content validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation and Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. The instrument was structured on a 4-point modified rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) with values 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach Alpha Statistics which yielded reliability indexes of 0.72, 0.86 and 0.84. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions with a criterion mean of 2.50. Questionnaire items with ratings below 2.50 denoted 'Low Extent' while 2.50 and above signified 'High Extent'. The hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. Analyzed data therefore with calculated z-value greater than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 was rejected and below was accepted.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent does online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Male and Female Facilitators on the Extent Online Quizzes Influence Students' Outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt Study Centre

S/ N	Item	Male Facilitator s N=41		Decisio n	Female Facilitator s N=32		Decisio n
		\bar{X}	SD		\bar{X}	SD	
1	Online quizzes help learners succeed individually by sharpening their focus and fostering deeper thinking	3.11	0.65	High Extent	3.19	0.50	High Extent
2	Online quizzes enhance students' attitude on learning by making them more prepared for class assessment	3.04	0.76	High Extent	2.69	0.69	High Extent
3	Online quizzes provide immediate feedback to students which enable them to verify their own knowledge of a particular subject	3.30	0.58	High Extent	3.25	0.52	High Extent
4	Online quizzes increase students' motivation and provide the opportunity for them to revise specific topics to catch up	3.09	0.53	High Extent	3.00	0.60	High Extent
5	Online quizzes encourage students to study continuously over a term which enhance their learning outcome	2.95	0.62	High Extent	2.77	0.72	High Extent
Grand Mean/SD		3.10	0.68		3.0	0.7	
					9	2	

Analyzed data in Table 1 for research question 1, revealed that all the items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 had mean scores 3.11, 3.04, 3.30, 3.09 and 2.95 with standard deviation 0.65, 0.76, 0.58, 0.53 and 0.62 for male facilitators and 3.19, 2.69, 3.25, 3.00 and 2.77 with standard deviation 0.50, 0.69, 0.52, 0.60 and 0.72 for female facilitators. In summary with grand mean scores of 3.10 and 3.09 which are above the criterion mean of 2.50, this indicated that

to a high extent online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Research Question 2: To what extent does online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Male and Female Facilitators on the Extent Online Discussion Influence Students' Outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt Study Centre.

S/ N	Item	Male Facilitators N=41		Decisio n	Female Facilitators N=32		Decisio n
		\bar{X}	SD		\bar{X}	SD	
6	Online discussions motivate learners to participate in class more by adding to discussions and asking questions	2.90	0.91	High Extent	2.85	0.88	High Extent
7	Online discussions enhance interaction and communication between students themselves and between students and the teacher significantly	2.85	1.11	High Extent	2.70	0.99	High Extent
8	Online discussions motivates shy and reserved students to contribute their opinions about a variety of topics, which boosts their confidence	2.80	1.05	High Extent	2.55	0.80	High Extent
9	Online discussions enable students reflect on their answers before posting them for others to read	2.95	0.93	High Extent	3.00	0.72	High Extent
10	Online discussion make learners take ownership of their own learning as they make decisions about tasks a discussion requires	2.75	0.89	High Extent	2.50	0.93	High Extent
Grand Mean/SD		2.85	0.98		2.72	0.86	

Data in Table 2 for research question 2, revealed that all the items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 had mean scores 2.90, 2.85, 2.80, 2.95 and 2.75 with standard deviation 0.91, 1.11, 1.05, 0.93 and 0.89 for male facilitators and 2.85, 2.70, 2.55, 3.00 and 2.50 with standard deviation 0.88, 0.99, 0.80, 0.72 and 0.93 for female facilitators. In summary with grand mean scores of 2.85 and 2.72 which are above the criterion mean of 2.50, this indicated that to a high extent online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Research Question 3: To what extent does peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Male and Female Facilitators on the Extent Peer Assessment Influence Students' Outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt Study Centre.

S/ N	Item	Male Facilitators N=41		Decisio n	Female Facilitator s N=32		Decisio n
		\bar{X}	SD		\bar{X}	SD	
11	Peer assessment enables learners reflect on their own efforts as well as enrich this reflection by exchanging feedback on their own and their peers' works	3.31	0.73	High Extent	3.16	0.70	High Extent
12	Peer assessment helps students develop lifelong skills in assessing and providing feedback to others	3.11	0.70	High Extent	3.02	0.51	High Extent
13	Peer assessment provides qualitative feedback that guide and help students in the revision of their work	2.98	0.69	High Extent	2.78	0.68	High Extent
14	Peer assessment enhances students' self-efficacy and promotes learner's autonomy	2.68	0.78	High Extent	2.50	0.62	High Extent

15	Peer assessment helps students develop lifelong skills of making reasoned justification of arguments	3.24	0.52	High Extent	3.01	0.59	High Extent
Grand Mean/SD		3.06	0.68		2.89	0.72	

Data in Table 3 for research question 3, revealed that all the items 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 had mean scores 3.31, 3.11, 2.98, 2.68 and 3.24 with standard deviation 0.73, 0.70, 0.69, 0.78 and 0.52 for male facilitators and 3.16, 3.02, 2.78, 2.50 and 3.01 with standard deviation 0.70, 0.51, 0.68, 0.62 and 0.59 for female facilitators. In summary with grand mean scores of 3.06 and 2.89 which are above the criterion mean of 2.50, this indicated that to a high extent peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Hypotheses

Ho1 There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Table 4: z-test Analysis of Difference Between the Mean Rating of Male and Female Facilitators on the Extent Online Quizzes Influence Students' Outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt Study Centre.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	SL	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Male Facilitators	41	3.10	0.68					Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
				71	0.05	0.06	± 1.96	
Female Facilitators	32	3.09	0.72					

Table 4 shows a summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre. The z-test calculated stood at 0.06 while the z-critical value was ± 1.96 , using 71 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Since the z-calculated was less than the z-critical, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Ho2 There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Table 5: z-test Analysis of Difference Between the Mean Rating of Male and Female Facilitators on the Extent Online Discussion Influence Students' Outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt Study Centre.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	SL	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Male Facilitators	41	2.85	0.98					Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
				71	0.05	0.59	± 1.96	
Female Facilitators	32	2.72	0.86					

Table 5 shows a summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre. The z-test calculated stood at 0.59 while the z-critical value was ± 1.96 , using 71 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Since the z-calculated was less than the z-critical, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of

male and female facilitators on the extent to which online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

H03 There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Table 6: z-test Analysis of Difference Between the Mean Rating of Male and Female Facilitators on the Extent Peer Assessment Influence Students' Outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt Study Centre.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	SL	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Male Facilitators	41	3.06	0.68					
				71	0.05	1.00	± 1.96	Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
Female Facilitators	32	2.89	0.72					

Table 6 shows a summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre. The z-test calculated stood at 1.00 while the z-critical value was ± 1.96 , using 71 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Since the z-calculated was less than the z-critical, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre.

Discussion of Findings

Findings on research question 1 on Table 1 revealed that to a very high extent online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre with grand mean scores of 3.10 and 3.09. Hypothesis 1 on Table 4 revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which online quizzes influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre with z-calculated value of 0.06 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . This finding is in agreement with Bognár, Fauszt and Váraljai (2021) who asserted that online quizzes strongly influence students' attitude on learning as a result, students perceive themselves as being more prepared for class meeting and more prepared for class assessments. Also in support, Nicol (2017) stated that online quizzes increase students' motivation and provides the opportunity for them to revise specific topics to catch up. As a result, students are encouraged to study continuously over a term.

Findings on research question 2 on Table 2 showed that to a high extent online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre with grand mean scores of 2.85 and 2.72. Again, information on hypothesis 2 on Table 5 revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which online discussion influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre with z-calculated value of 0.59 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . This finding corroborates with Harris and Sander (2017) who stated that online discussion make learners take ownership of their own learning as they make decisions about the postings to read, the questions to ask, and the comments to post, among other tasks a discussion requires. The finding is also in tandem with Biriya and Thomas in Lyu (2018) who argued that increased student participation is one of the

immediate benefits of participating in online discussions as it influences interaction and communication between students themselves and between students and the teacher significantly.

Findings on research question 3 on Table 3 showed that to a very high extent peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre with grand mean scores of 3.06 and 2.89. Again, information on hypothesis 3 on Table 6 revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female facilitators on the extent to which peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre with z-calculated value of 1.00 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . This finding in tandem with Orsmond (2015) who asserted that engaging students in peer assessment can help them in learning to evaluate their own learning and in interpreting assessment criteria. Also in corroboration, Amendola and Miceli (2018) found evidence that students participating in peer assessment developed their skills of making reasoned justification of arguments.

CONCLUSION

In view of the results obtained from this study, it was concluded that to a high extent online quizzes, online discussion and peer assessment influence students' outcome in National Open University in Port Harcourt study centre. Through tailored evaluation methods, online assessment not only gauge comprehension but also foster engagement of students and ultimately enhancing learning outcomes in the digital realm of distance education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Facilitators should design online quizzes that align closely with course objectives and incorporate a variety of question types to cater for diverse learning styles.
2. Facilitators should establish clear guidelines and incorporate diverse discussion formats to accommodate different learning preferences.
3. Facilitators should provide appropriate training to enable students familiarize themselves with the process of grading their peers' assignments so that more knowledge would be gained by the student on the subject's contents.

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